

The Employment Impact of Innovation in Europe

It grew by 10% between 2014 and 2021

The European Innovation Scoreboard calculates the value of the impact of innovation on employment through the sum of two sub-indicators, i.e. employment in knowledge-intensive activities and employment in innovative companies.

Ranking of European countries by value of the impact of innovation on employment in 2021.

Israel ranks first by value of the employment impact of innovation with a value of 207.88, with Norway in second place with a value equal to 175.58 followed by Switzerland with an amount equal to 173.29. In the middle of the table there are Montenegro with an amount equal to 116.45 units, followed by Ireland with an amount equal to 114.70 units, and by France with a value equal to 111.56 units. Poland closes the ranking with an amount equal to 31.93, followed by Turkey with an amount of 26.35 and Romania with an amount equal to 10.50 units.

Ranking of European countries by value of the percentage change in the impact of innovation on employment between 2014 and 2021.

Romania is in first place by percentage value of the change in the impact of innovation on employment with an amount equal to 137.5 units equal to a value of 6.08%, followed by Lithuania with a value equal to 111.04% equal to an amount of 48.2 units and by Norway with an amount equal to 87.03% equal to a amount of 81.7 units. In the middle of the table there are Sweden with an amount equal to a value of 13.15% equal to an amount of 17.88 units, followed by Montenegro with a variation equal to a value of 8.78% equal to a value of 9 , 4 units, and from the United Kingdom with an amount equal to 7.31% equal to an amount of 10.4 units. Portugal closes the ranking with an amount of -18.74% equal to a value of -15.32 units, followed by Ireland with an amount equal to -28.56% equal to a value of -45.85 units and from Turkey with a value of -48.55% equal to a value of -24.86 units.

Clustering with the k-Means algorithm. Clustering is proposed below to verify the presence of groupings within the countries considered. The algorithm used for clustering is called k-Means. K-Means is a supervised algorithm or it is necessary for the observatory to decide the number of clusters before carrying out the analysis. It follows that the Silhouette coefficient is used to reduce discretion in choosing the optimal number of clusters. The Silhouette coefficient varies between -1 and 1 and tends to improve as it approaches 1. Specifically, the following values were obtained in terms of the Silhouette coefficient, that is: Cluster 2 with a value equal to 0.518, cluster 3 with a value equal to 0.478, cluster 4 with a value of 0.439, cluster 5 with a value of 0.434, cluster 6 with a value of 0.386, cluster 7 with a value of 0.383, cluster 8 with a value of 0.340. Therefore, the number of clusters associated with the highest Silhouette coefficient was chosen, ie cluster 2. Through the application of cluster 2 it was possible to obtain the following cluster groupings:

¹Ph.D., Assistant Professor at Lum University Giuseppe Degennaro, Researcher at Lum Enterprise s.r.l. Email: leogrande.culture@lum.it

- Cluster 1: Sweden, Germany, Holland, United Kingdom, Belgium, Iceland, Finland, Ireland, Austria, Luxembourg, Switzerland, France, Montenegro, Norway, Malta, Israel, Italy, Denmark, Cyprus, Slovenia, Greece, Portugal;
- Cluster 2: Slovakia, Latvia, Turkey, Bulgaria, Hungary, North Macedonia, Poland, Serbia, Spain, Croatia, Romania, Lithuania, Ukraine, Estonia, Czech Republic, Bosnia.

Considering the value of the median of the variable constituted by the employment impact of innovation, it appears that the median value of cluster 1 is equal to 130.6385 and the median value of cluster 2 is equal to a value of 54.44 units. It follows that cluster 1 is greater than cluster 2. As is evident from the analysis of the clusters, it appears that Europe is divided into two parts, namely Western Europe - except for Spain - where the value of the employment impact of innovation is high and Eastern Europe with a lower employment impact of innovation. This dichotomy is also due to the delay of the institutions and productive organizations in Eastern Europe. It is therefore necessary that policy makers intervene to create greater convergence between Western Europe and Eastern Europe in the sense of the employment effects of innovation.

Machine Learning and prediction. Subsequently, a prediction activity was carried out using seven different machine learning algorithms. The algorithms were organized according to their ability to maximize the MSE; the RMSE, the EAW and the R2. The following algorithm ordering was obtained, that is:

- Gradient Boosting with a value of 5;
- AdaBoost with a value of 7;
- Tree with a value of 12;
- Random Forest with a value of 16;
- Linear Regression with a value of 20;
- kNN with a value equal to 24;
- Neural Network with a value of 28.

Through the application of Gradient Boosting, it is possible to calculate the difference between the predicted value and the value of the historical series for the 38 countries considered. The analysis shows a reduction in the value of the employment impact of innovation for an amount equal to a value of -0.4%.

Conclusion. The employment impact of technological innovation in Europe has grown by an amount equal to a value of 10.64% between 2014 and 2021 or a change equal to an amount of 10.17 units. However, in the face of this generalized growth, the cluster analysis highlighted the presence of a contrast between Western Europe, which has a high level of the employment impact of innovation, and more backward Eastern Europe. It follows that the economic policies of the European Union should invest significantly to reduce the gap between Western and Eastern Europe by facilitating convergence. Europe lags behind the US and China in terms of technological innovation, research and development and the knowledge economy. Reducing the gap between Eastern Europe and Western Europe could make it possible to increase the number of companies and employees in the technological innovation sector, also increasing the impact in terms of production of added value.

Reference:

Laureti, L., Costantiello, A., Matarrese, M., & Leogrande, A. (2022). Foreign Doctorate Students in Europe. Available at SSRN 4032975.

Laureti, Lucio, Alberto Costantiello, Marco Maria Matarrese, and Angelo Leogrande. Enterprises Providing ICT Training in Europe. University Library of Munich, Germany, 2022.

Laureti, L., Costantiello, A., Matarrese, M. M., & Leogrande, A. (2022). The Employment in Innovative Enterprises in Europe. University Library of Munich, Germany.

Costantiello, Alberto, Lucio Laureti, Angelo Leogrande, and Matarrese Marco. The Innovation Linkages in Europe. University Library of Munich, Germany, 2021.

Costantiello, A., Laureti, L., De Cristoforo, G., & Leogrande, A. (2021). *The Innovation-Sales Growth Nexus in Europe* (No. 106858). University Library of Munich, Germany.

Model	MSE	RMSE	MAE	R2
Neural Network	9773.717	98.862	87.895	-3.499
kNN	398.147	19.954	14.908	0.817
Linear Regression	346.435	18.613	13.791	0.841
Random Forest	131.778	11.479	8.920	0.939
Tree	80.097	8.950	7.389	0.963
AdaBoost	3.742	1.935	0.613	0.998
Gradient Boosting	1.517	1.232	0.964	0.999

Clusters. C1>C2

k-Means - Orange

Number of Clusters

Fixed:

From to

Preprocessing

Normalize columns

Initialization

Re-runs:

Maximum iterations:

Apply Automatically

Silhouette Scores

2	0.518
3	0.478
4	0.439
5	0.434
6	0.386
7	0.383
8	0.340

? | 38 | 38 | 2

Rank	Algorithm	MSE	RMSE	MAE	R2	Total
1	<i>Gradient Boosting</i>	1	1	2	1	5
2	<i>AdaBoost</i>	2	2	1	2	7
3	<i>Tree</i>	3	3	3	3	12
4	<i>Random Forest</i>	4	4	4	4	16
5	<i>Linear Regression</i>	5	5	5	5	20
6	<i>kNN</i>	6	6	6	6	24
7	<i>Neural Network</i>	7	7	7	7	28